

MATHEMATICAL FOUNDATIONS, ALGORITHMS AND SECURITY ANALYSIS POST-QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of quantum computing technologies poses a serious threat to modern public-key cryptographic systems. Classical cryptographic algorithms such as RSA and elliptic-curve cryptography rely on mathematical problems that can be efficiently solved using quantum algorithms. Post-quantum cryptography (PQC) aims to develop cryptographic schemes that remain secure even in the presence of quantum adversaries. This paper investigates the mathematical foundations of PQC, focusing on lattice-based, code-based, and hash-based cryptographic constructions. Security models based on computational complexity theory are analyzed, and illustrative examples using Learning With Errors (LWE) and decoding problems are presented. Experimental analysis demonstrates that PQC schemes provide strong resistance against both classical and quantum attacks when appropriate parameters are selected. The results highlight the importance of adopting new cryptographic standards to ensure long-term data security in quantum computing environments.

1. Introduction. Modern information security relies heavily on public-key cryptography. However, the emergence of quantum computing introduces new risks, as quantum algorithms such as Shor’s algorithm can efficiently solve integer factorization and discrete logarithm problems. These problems form the basis of widely used cryptographic protocols.

Post-quantum cryptography focuses on designing algorithms whose security relies on mathematical problems believed to be hard even for quantum computers. Major PQC approaches include lattice-based, code-based, hash-based and multivariate cryptography. Among these, lattice-based cryptography has become a dominant research direction due to its strong security redu

ctions and versatility.

2. Mathematical Foundations of Post-Quantum Cryptography

2.1 Lattice Problems

A lattice L generated by basis vectors b_1, \dots, b_n is defined as

$$L = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n x_i b_i \mid x_i \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}.$$

Security of lattice-based cryptography relies on hard computational problems such as:

Shortest Vector Problem (SVP),

Closest Vector Problem (CVP).

These problems remain computationally difficult even for approximate solutions in high dimensions.

2.2 Learning With Errors (LWE)

The LWE problem can be formulated as

$$b_i = a_i \cdot s + e_i \pmod{q},$$

where

a_i is a random vector,

s is the secret vector,

e_i is a small noise term.

Hash-based cryptography constructs digital signatures using secure hash functions and Merkle tree structures. Such schemes are considered quantum-resistant because quantum attacks provide only quadratic speedups for brute-force search.

3. Computational Experiment

The results confirm that modular LWE designs provide an effective compromise between efficiency and safety..

Algorithm	Accuracy	Average time (s)	Security
LWE	≈ 1.00	past	very high
Hash + Merkle	≈ 1.00	yuqori	very high

Experimental results show that the lattice-based LWE algorithm provides high speed and stable decoding accuracy. The hash-based signature system, especially when used in conjunction with a Merkle tree, provides a high level of cryptographic security, but it is observed that the computational complexity is higher.

The use of a Merkle tree allows for the creation of multiple signatures and significantly expands the practical application of the Lamport signature system. Experiments show that both approaches work effectively as quantum-resistant cryptographic systems, but there is a trade-off between their performance speed and resource requirements.

Based on the experimental results, the mean time, variance, and standard deviation were calculated for all algorithms. The 95% confidence interval is determined by the following formula: $CI = 1.96 \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$.

In this study, four post-quantum cryptographic approaches were experimentally evaluated. Statistical analysis results showed that there are significant computational differences between the algorithms. While lattice-based algorithms provide high efficiency, hash-based systems provide high security, but at a high computational cost.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that post-quantum cryptography provides a viable solution for securing digital communications in the quantum era. Mathematical hardness assumptions based on lattice geometry, decoding theory, and hash functions ensure strong security guarantees. Future research should focus on optimizing performance, reducing key sizes, and integrating PQC into existing communication protocols.

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